

ELASTIC DEFORMATION BEHAVIORS OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

Quan Gaofeng, Chai Donglang & Song Yujiu

*State Key Laboratory for Mechanical Behavior of Materials,
Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, 710049 P.R.China*

SUMMARY: The elastic deformation of particulate reinforced aluminum and magnesium alloy matrix composites are both experimentally and analytically studied. The materials are made by P/M method. It is found that there are great differences in elastic deformation performances between composite materials and controlled alloys. The composites have much higher elastic moduli than controlled alloys, and the higher the content of the ceramic particles is, the higher the modulus is. Moreover, most composites in this work have much higher elastic limits than those of the controlled materials. The analytical studies, with simple quasi-tri-dimensional models for the both, also clarify these rises, and can give out some better quantitative estimations.

KEY WORDS: Al and Mg alloy matrix composites, elastic deformation, modulus, elastic limits, particle content, quantitative analysis, mechanical property estimation

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites have achieved great attention both in materials science and engineering application fields due to their superiority in mechanical property and performance, especially reinforced with short fibers and/or particles. Even though a number of studies are focused on their fabricating method, fracture performance, interfacial characterizations, etc., there is no denying the fact that almost any component and/or structure is working during service within elastic deformation stage. Up till now there is not much analytical work on the behavior of elastic or small deformation of the composites, and a lot of digital computation work is taken with various models on stress-strain behavior of the composites with regular meso-structures [1,2]. Previous work of the present author has clarified that the particulate reinforced metal matrix composites have excellent strength properties which can be analyzed quantitatively with a mechanical model by some fuzzy theoretical treatments [3,4]. The elastic modulus (Young's modulus) is the most important both mechanics and physics parameter for a specific structural composite, which has been modeled by many researchers [5]. But most of the models have not included the interactions of stress fields of the neighboring particles, which may be a unavoidable factor of discrepancy in calculated results and the practical measured ones. In this work the elastic moduli of some aluminum and magnesium alloy matrix composites contained various contents of SiCp (silicon carbide particles) are measured and analyzed with a consideration of interactions of neighboring particles. Also the engineering elastic limits of them are determined and interpreted with a previous proposed model.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

SiC_p reinforced aluminum (SAE2024) and magnesium alloy matrix composites are fabricated by P/M method (The former is called aluminum composite, the latter called magnesium composite for short). The normal sizes of the particles are 5μm, 10μm, and 20μm, and the metal or alloy powder's size are ranged from 5μm to 54μm. The compositions of the matrix are given in Table 1. The volume fractions of SiC_p are from 0.05 to 0.40. The mixtures of the ceramic and metal powders are cold-pressed in a mold, hot-pressed and followed by hot-extrusion (extrusion ratio 1:16) and heat-treatment (T6, solutioned and aged to about peak hardness). The round tension samples are machined to measure the stress-strain curve (see Fig. 4), on which the elastic limit (engineering proportional limit), proof stress, ultimate strength and ductility are determined on an INSTRON1195 testing machine. The elastic moduli are determined from both microstrain and a linear regression method on the straight length of the curves.

Table 1: The Compositions of The Matrix Alloys

Alloy / Chemistry	Al	Mg	Si	Cu	Zn	Mn	Zr	Fe
Aluminum(2024)	Bal.	1.6	<0.20	4.55	<0.10	0.10		<0.10
Magnesium(MB15*)		Bal.			5.00		0.60	

* MB15 is a Chinese Brand of Mg-Zn-Zr alloy

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF ELASTIC MODULUS

Measured Modulus of Aluminum Composites

The practical measured elastic moduli of the aluminum composites are showed in Fig. 1, in which the increasing tendency in elastic modulus with the ceramic particle volume fraction is very outstanding. The increase in elastic modulus is one of the most interesting features of these materials, and less affected by the fabricating routine but the constituents and their distributions. In this work the superior orientation of the long axis of ellipsoid-like particles to the extrusion direction is found and the expectation of the specific ratio are analyzed. The superior orientation may cause the axial elastic modulus to increase more. In the extreme situation in this work, the maximum elastic modulus of the composite containing a SiC_p fraction of 0.40 is as high as 168.7 GPa, which is 2.41 times of the matrix alloys.

Elastic Modulus Results of Magnesium Composites

Table 2 shows the measured results of elastic modulus in magnesium composites, companied with the specific modulus and strength data, and as a comparison the aluminum composites' data enclosed. It is also seen that the moduli of the composites increase greatly. It can be noticed that in the same table the absolute property value of magnesium composites may not be superior to those of aluminum composites, but the specific value of the formers have some advantages in air and space applications.

Fig. 1: Elastic moduli of aluminum and magnesium composites vs volume fraction of SiCp

Table 2: Property data of Magnesium composites vs those of aluminum composites

Material	E , GPa	σ_p , MPa	ρ , g/cm ³	E/ρ , 10 ⁶ m	σ_p/ρ , 10 ³ m
Magnesium(MB15)	45	180	1.76	2.609	10.436
0.10SiC _p /MB15	67.0	266.0	1.904	3.591	14.250
0.20SiC _p /MB15	79.5	274.3	2.05	3.957	15.900
0.20SiC _p /2024	112	318.0	2.89	3.954	11.228

Analysis of The Modulus for Particles Reinforcing Composites

According to a multi-particle model, in which a consideration of interactions of neighboring stress fields of the particles is introduced with superposition at the spherical shell surface of a radius of R , which is defined as the half-distance of neighboring particles. Let E_0 be the modulus of the composite, ν_0 the Poisson ratio, K_0 the volume modulus, and G_0 the shear modulus, and $\eta = a/R$ the spacing ratio of the particles (suppose all particles spacially homogeneous distribution, a is the normal radius of the particles). So we obtain such an expression [8]:

$$\frac{2E_0}{3(1-\nu_0)} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{V_i}{\frac{1}{4G_0} - \frac{\eta^3}{3K_0} + \frac{1+\eta^3}{3K_i}} \quad (1)$$

where V_i represents the volume fraction of the constituents, the whole composite can be treated as two constituents: the matrix and reinforcement, so $V_1=1-V_p$, $V_2=V_p$. And K_i represents the volume modulus of the constituents. As soon as the distribution pattern is certain, the relation between V_p and η is solely certain. For instance, the relation of the two parameters for a simply body-centered cubic distribution can be written as:

$$\eta^3 = 1.4702 V_p \quad (2)$$

This equation also is a limitation of the application of Equ.1, i.e., $(V_p)_{\max} 0.68$. The v_0 can be determined by other method, i.e., ROM method [6]:

$$v_0 = \sum_{i=1}^m V_i v_i \tag{3}$$

Fig. 2: Comparisons of Present model with Kuster & Toksoz’s Model and Experimental data

Fig. 2 show the estimations of moduli from Equ. 1 for the aluminum (diamond mark) and magnesium (square mark) composites, also the practically measured data. It is obviously seen that the present model would more accurate than Kuster and Toksoz’s model (triangle mark)[7]. The higher points at 0.150.20 of volume fraction than the estimations is caused by longer oriented silicon carbide particles (the average axial specific ratio equals 2.17), which were produced by different factories.

RESISTANCE TO ELASTIC DEFORMATION BEHAVIORS

Elastic Deformation Patterns of Composites with Various Contents of Particles

Elastic deformation resistance has most important significance in both material and structure design, also in working life of machines. Almost all practical mechanisms are required not to be deformed elastically over a given amount. In more exact meaning, the elastic limit σ_e is used as a design parameter, but in most application situations the engineering proportional limits, σ_p is adopted as both design parameter and criterion of material qualification. In this work they are measured by the way that the intersection of the tension curve and the straight line with a 50% slope of straight length of the tension curve is taken as σ_p point. The results are showed in Fig. 3.

These results illustrate that the σ_p is increasing with the volume fraction of SiC_p, and this is merely found in published work. Also, σ_p of magnesium composites are much higher than the controlled alloy. This is more profitable to all mechanical applications, especially in aerospace structures. The increase in proportional limits of the composites has also confirmed the appropriateness of the fabricating techniques. Fig. 4 is the copies of the local tensile curves of some typical materials, which show a direct evidence of the increases in elastic limits and elastic moduli.

Fig. 3 Engineering proportional limits of the composites

Fig. 4 Recorded stress-strain curves of aluminum composites

Analysis and Verification for Elastic Limits of DRMMCs

According to a previous model proposed by the present authors [3], in which the meso-structure distribution in the composites can be seen as a body-centered cubic pattern, the lower and upper elastic limits are written as:

$$\sigma_{cp}^l = \begin{cases} [1 + A_2(k_c^L E_2 / E_1 - 1)]\sigma_{mp}, & \sigma_z / \tilde{\sigma}_1 \geq 1 \\ \frac{1 + A_2(k_c^L E_2 / E_1 - 1)}{\omega_1 + \omega_2 k_c^L E_2 / E_1} \sigma_{mp}, & \sigma_z / \tilde{\sigma}_1 < 1 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{cp}^u = \begin{cases} \frac{1 + A_2(k_c^L E_2 / E_1 - 1)}{\omega_1 + \omega_2 k_c^L E_2 / E_1} \sigma_{mp}, & \sigma_z / \tilde{\sigma}_1 \geq 1 \\ [1 + A_2(k_c^L E_2 / E_1 - 1)]\sigma_{mp}, & \sigma_z / \tilde{\sigma}_1 < 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $k_c^L = \frac{2\eta^2}{1+\eta^2} \frac{\lambda}{1+\lambda}$ is defined as “striain constraint factor”, and ω_1 and ω_2 are the structural parameters determined by a , R , l and V_p , E_1 and E_2 are the elastic moduli of the matrix and reinforcement, respectively, A_2 is the area fraction of the reinforcement on an arbitrary cross section. σ_z and $\tilde{\sigma}_1$ are the equivalent stress at the top of the particle and the effective axial stress in the matrix by the particle. Some attention must be paid that the real elastic limit of a specific composite is inevitably fallen between σ_{cp}^l and σ_{cp}^u .

From the two estimate formula one can be sure to determine the range of elastic limit of a particular composite whose meso-structural parameters are known. Fig. 5 shows the estimated results. It is necessary to question that the residual micro- and meso-stresses between the constituents must have some effect on the elastic limit, especially in the matrix with lower elastic limit.

Fig. 5: Estimate results from Eqs. (4, 5) and comparison with experimental data (Xpu-Al-0 means the upper elastic limit and the both residual stresses are zero for aluminum composites, and Xpl-Al-50 denotes the lower elastic limit and the interfacial residual stresses are equal to 50MPa, and so forth).

As a rational deduction the superposition method further can be introduced to deal with the problem. If the effective radial residual stress near the interface between a particle and the matrix is $\langle \sigma_r^R \rangle$ and the tangential stress is $\langle \sigma_\psi^R \rangle$ [5], then the real elastic limits (lower and

upper) can be determined by σ_{mp} with $\sigma_{mp} - \langle \sigma_r^R \rangle$ in the first formula of Equ. 5, and σ_{mp} with $\sigma_{mp} - \langle \sigma_\psi^R \rangle$ in the second one. Fig. 5 also gives the estimations which include the interfacial residual stresses. In the light of the situation with presumed regular residual stress consideration, the elastic limits vary very much. Actually the residual stresses are not constant in different position and near different particles, and that needs more complicated model to deal with.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The composite materials made by P/M method have much higher resistance to elastic deformation, illustrated by both higher elastic modulus E and higher elastic limit σ_{cp} .
2. A model to evaluate the modulus of composites including interactions of neibeghring particles is proposed and a better agreement with the experimental data has been achieved.
3. An analytical model for estimation of elastic limits of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites is applied to interpret the increase in elastic limits of the composites, in which the difference in stress at different position of the matrix causes the estimation to drop in the range of lower and upper elastic limits. Experimental results seem to support the model.

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